

THE LIGHT SCATTERING BEHAVIOUR OF THORIUM ARSENATE GEL-FORMING SYSTEMS

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The changes in the depolarisation and the intensity of transversely scattered light and opacity of thorium arsenate gels, obtained by diluting acid solution of thorium arsenate, have been investigated. The results show that the colloidal particles formed by diluting acid solution of thorium arsenate become hydrated and the gels are formed. During gelation there are no changes in the size and shape of the particles. The gel particles, which are anisotropic and comparable with the wave-length of light used, seem to be disc-shaped.

Thorium arsenate gels are known to be formed either by metathesis between potassium arsenate and thorium nitrate or by diluting an acid solution of thorium arsenate. The literature reveals that gels formed by the former technique have received good attention, whereas those arising out of the latter method have escaped attention. It was therefore thought worth-while to study the optical properties of thorium arsenate gel-forming systems formed by diluting acid solution of thorium arsenate.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thorium arsenate was prepared by adding an excess of potassium arsenate to a solution of thorium nitrate and washing the gelatinous precipitate free of impurities by hot distilled water and drying in an air-oven at 110°. Thorium arsenate (30 g.) was then dissolved in 2.926N-HCl (250 c.c.). Thorium content was found to be 3.14%. A known volume of this solution, when diluted to different extents with distilled water, gave transparent to translucent gels.

Depolarisation factors of the transversely scattered light were measured by Cornu's method, taking all the necessary precautions.

The intensity of transversely scattered light was measured by a photoelectric method using a photomultiplier tube. The details of the circuit arrangement are given in a recent publication (cf. Sundaram and Desai, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci.*, 1954, 20, 597).

The opacity of the gel-forming mixture was measured by using the Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter. Distilled water was taken as blank.

The solutions used for preparing the gel-forming mixtures were made dust-free by repeated filtration through sintered glass filters.

The results obtained for the depolarisation values and the intensity as well as opacity measurements for gel-forming mixtures containing 4 c.c. of thorium arsenate solution, diluted to 52 c.c. or 72 c.c., are shown in Tables I and II. The following notations have been used in these tables.

T = time (min.) from the commencement of dilution of the acid solution.

t = time of setting of gel (min.).

O and I = opacity and intensity readings measured in arbitrary units.
The depolarisation values ρ_u , ρ_v , ρ_h are expressed as percentages.

TABLE I

Thorium arsenate = 4.0 c.c. Total volume = 52.0 c.c. $t = 4$ mins.

T.	ρ_u .	ρ_v .	ρ_h .	I .	O .	$I_{45^\circ}/I_{135^\circ}$.
1	3.80	1.30	...	8.0	0.0	4.0
2	3.80	...	59.95	8.0	0.0	4.0
3	3.82	1.30	59.95	9.0	1.0	4.10
4	3.96	...	...	11.5	7.5	...
5	4.14	1.30	56.79	12.0	12.0	4.08
7	4.14	...	...	13.0	19.0	...
10	4.33	1.30	...	15.5	26.5	4.12
15	...	...	49.03	19.0	37.0	...
20	4.52	1.30	...	22.5	46.0	4.48
25	4.71	...	...	25.0	51.5	...
30	...	1.40	46.36	26.5	55.0	4.60
40	4.71	...	...	32.0	62.5	...
60	...	1.51	...	36.5	67.5	4.63
80	4.92	...	44.65	40.0	72.0	...
100	4.92	1.51	43.81	40.5	73.5	4.68

TABLE II

Thorium arsenate = 4.0 c.c. Total volume = 72.0 c.c. $t = 10$ mins.

T.	ρ_u .	ρ_v .	ρ_h .	I .	O .	$I_{45^\circ}/I_{135^\circ}$.
1	2.80	1.11	...	7.0	0.0	3.80
2	2.80	1.11	64.58	7.0	0.0	...
3	2.80	...	...	7.0	0.0	...
4	2.80	1.11	64.58	7.0	0.0	...
5	2.80	1.11	64.58	7.0	0.0	...
7	2.80	...	...	7.0	0.0	3.80
9	2.80	1.11	...	7.0	0.0	...
10	2.95	...	63.27	8.0	1.5	...
15	...	1.20	...	8.5	2.0	3.96
25	3.11	...	61.04	10.0	6.5	...
30	3.27	1.30	...	10.0	14.0	4.11
40	3.27	...	59.95	10.5	15.5	...
60	3.43	...	...	10.5	18.5	4.23
80	...	1.40	57.82	11.0	22.0	...
100	3.61	1.40	56.79	12.5	24.0	4.30
				13.5	25.0	4.32

DISCUSSION

Depolarisation Measurements.—It will be observed from the results recorded in Tables I and II that till about the gelation time, the values of ρ_u , ρ_v and ρ_h remain almost constant. It is further noticed that in these systems the values of ρ_u , ρ_v and ρ_h begin to change from near about the setting time and that these changes continue until they become almost constant. Since the values of ρ_u , ρ_v and ρ_h remain constant during the process of gel-formation, it may be concluded that there are no perceptible changes in the size and shape of the colloidal particles during the process of gel-formation. The departure from the zero value of ρ_v in these gels suggests that the gel-particles are anisotropic. The low values of ρ_h in these gels reveal that the particles are not very small as compared to the wave-length of light. The values of ρ_u , ρ_v and ρ_h seem to undergo continuous changes from just near about the setting time. From the study of their actual values it is clear that the particles in the set gels begin to grow in size and increase in anisotropy.

It has been reported (cf. Prasad and Guruswamy, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1944, 19A, 66; Desai and Sundaram, *loc. cit.*; *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1954, 23, 9) that in the gel-forming systems of thorium arsenate, formed by metathetical reaction, the colloid particles increase in size and anisotropy during gelation and that these changes continue even after the gels have set. From the increase in the values of I_D they have concluded that the process of gel-formation, as revealed by the study of thorium arsenate, is analogous to coagulation.

Opacity and Intensity Measurements.—The changes in the values of opacity and intensity of transversely scattered light during and after the process of gel-formation are recorded in Tables I and II. It will be seen that the values of opacity and intensity are almost constant till about the setting time and thereafter there is a continuous increase in opacity and intensity, and that they tend to approach constant values. Similar changes have been observed for the intensity of light scattered in the forward and backward directions. These results indicate that there are no changes in the size, shape and/or number of gel-forming particles and that hydration does not affect opacity and intensity values. The increase in the values of opacity and intensity from near about the setting point suggests that in the freshly prepared thorium arsenate gels, there are changes in the size, shape and/or number of gel particles during the process of ageing. These observations, thus, support the conclusions drawn from the measurements of depolarisation factors.

Density and Anisotropy Scatterings.—The density and the anisotropy scatterings have been separately calculated for one system by using the equations,

$$I_D = I \cdot \frac{6-7\rho}{6+6\rho} \quad \text{and} \quad I_A = I - I_D$$

where I_D = density scattering and I_A = anisotropy scattering, from the values of the intensity and depolarisation factors of the transversely scattered light and the values thus obtained are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Thorium arsenate = 4 c.c. Total volume = 52.0 c.c.

T .	ρ_v .	$\rho = \frac{2\rho_v}{1+\rho_v}$.	$\frac{6-7\rho}{6+6\rho}$.	I_{90° .	$I_D = I_{90^\circ} \cdot \frac{6-7\rho}{6+6\rho}$.	$I_A = I_{90^\circ} - I_D$.
1 mm.	1.30	0.0257	0.9442	8.0	7.55	0.45
2	1.30	0.0257	0.9442	8.0	7.55	0.45
3	1.30	0.0257	0.9442	9.0	8.50	0.50
4	1.30	0.0257	0.9442	11.5	10.86	0.60
5	1.30	0.0257	0.9442	12.0	11.33	0.67
7	1.30	0.0257	0.9442	13.0	12.27	0.73
10	1.30	0.0257	0.9442	15.5	14.64	0.86
20	1.30	0.0257	0.9442	22.5	21.24	1.26
30	1.40	0.0276	0.9413	26.5	24.95	1.54
60	1.51	0.0298	0.9373	36.5	34.21	2.29
80	1.51	0.0298	0.9373	47.0	37.43	2.51
100	1.51	0.0298	0.9373	40.5	37.95	2.54

As there are practically no changes in the values of I_D and I_A during gelation, it may be concluded that during this process there are no changes in the size, number and shape of the colloid particles. It is seen further that the scattering intensity is mostly due to density scattering in the initial stages and that throughout the process of ageing, the density scattering predominates over the anisotropy scattering.

Dissymmetry Ratio $I_{45^\circ}/I_{135^\circ}$.—In order to get some idea about the gel particles in the systems investigated, the ratio $I_{45^\circ}/I_{135^\circ}$ has been calculated from the measurements of the intensity of scattered light in the forward and backward directions and the results are shown in Tables I and II.

It is seen from the tables that the values of this ratio continuously increase only from about the gelation time and that it attains constant values sometime after the setting of gels, which indicate the increase in the size of the particles during ageing. The value of the ratios in fresh gels appears to be approximately 4. In the gel-systems studied in the present investigation, the particle size is fairly large, as can be inferred from the low values of ρ_h in the gel state. Although in gel-systems the particles cannot be considered to be independent of each other, yet from the values of the dissymmetry ratio one may infer that the particles in the thorium arsenate gels are probably disc-shaped. This conclusion is in harmony with the one drawn by Desai and Sundaram (*loc. cit.*) in the case of thorium arsenate gel-systems formed by metathetical reaction.

Effect of Dilution.—Tables I and II show that the values of ρ_h and ρ_v are relatively low for the gel containing greater amount of distilled water, that is, in less acidic medium. The values of ρ_h in the system containing greater amount of distilled water are relatively high. This means that in more dilute system the gel particles are relatively small and less anisotropic. This may probably be due to the formation of smaller and less anisotropic aggregates in loose systems wherein the amount of water seems to be more than what is required for the hydration of colloid particles.

The higher rate of change in opacity and in intensity of scattered light in the relatively less dilute system may be similarly accounted for.

Mechanism of Gel-formation.—When an acid solution of thorium arsenate is suitably diluted, thorium arsenate is thrown out because of the reduction in its solubility in the diluted acid. These particles then are held in colloid dimensions, as can be inferred from the depolarisation data. These particles then become heavily hydrated with the formation of the gels. During gelation there are practically no changes in size and shape of the colloid particles. This is revealed by the measurement of the depolarisation factors, intensity and opacity of these systems during gelation.

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